

Questions, Comments and Answers following the presentation

GPI calibrations Fredrik Rantakyro

Mouillet: Polarimetric standards are not observed on a regular basis anymore. Why? Because instrument polarisation is stable enough? or difficult to use?

For the accuracy of the instrument the instrument is stable enough. It is foreseen that if a certain program requires higher than standard accuracy the program can request non baseline polarimetric standards.

Milli: What is the QC parameters used by GPI? Is tau used as a constraint?

The pipeline delivers the final delivered contrast for one frame and that is used in the QC0 evaluation. For modes where there is no satellite spots like the Direct (non coronagraph modes) the measured Wavefront error is used or the measured DIMM/MASS seeing, same for the NRM/SAM modes. The tau is a good indicator but not as strongly correlated with the final performance so the measured WFE is the best indicator.

Roth: Comment: Concerning the issue of taking detector flats (rather than IFU flats), we have experimented with PMAS at Calar Alto to defocus the spectrograph, model the defocused spectra, and then determine the pixel-to-pixel variation of the detector response. However, the contribution to the total error was negligible.

A very good suggestion, unfortunately we have no possibility of defocusing the lens wrt the detector.